

A Study of Fluorescein as a Ligand. Part—VI

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Fluorescein has been investigated as a ligand and oscillator strengths have been calculated, from spectral data, in acidic media as well as in various pH ranges.

FLUORESCHEIN was first prepared by Baeyer as back as in the year 1871 and assigned a lactoid structure. Kopp and Decker⁶ and Pope *et al*⁷ gave cogent reasons for a *p*-quinoid structure to the molecule. Orndroff⁸ has shown that fluorescein exists in two isomeric forms, red and yellow, the latter with a lactoid and former with *p*-quinoid one. The present authors undertook a study of fluorescein under two aspects, (i) to study it as a ligand for the complexes already reported¹⁻⁵ and adducts to be reported⁹ and (ii) to determine the oscillator strengths in various media.

Experimental

Fluorescein was obtained from B.D.H., Poole (England) and was purified by dissolving in a strong solution of NaOH and precipitating it fresh by Analar HCl. The elemental analysis is given below :

Analysis :

Found : C, 72.28 ; H, 3.71 ; Calculated for C₂₀H₁₂O₈ C, 72.30 ; H, 3.60.

The red crystalline sample, so obtained, was found to dissolve sparingly in methanol, ethanol, acetic acid, nitrobenzene and formic acid. It dissolved readily in hot aniline, formic acid and acetone.

Spectra were recorded on an automatic and range adjustable Pye-Unicam SP 8-100 Spectrophotometer which was previously checked and adjusted by a dydium glass spectrum. Diffuse reflectance spectra were recorded with the special attachment to SP-500 by disc method, MgO being the standard.

Infra-red wavelengths were obtained on Perkin-Elmer 137-1281 Infracord. Both the KBr pellet technique and the nujol mull method were employed.

The magnetic measurement of the samples were taken on a simple Guoy balance at room temperature.

Results and Discussion

The electronic absorption spectral data of fluorescein is given in Table 1 and the characteristic wave numbers (cm⁻¹) in the I.R. spectrum of the sample with probable assignments are given in Table 2.

TABLE 1—ELECTRONIC ABSORPTION SPECTRA OF FLUORESCHEIN

Solvents	Dielectric constant (ε)	λ _(max) nm	log F _m
Formic acid	58.52	391, 397	3.36, 2.76
Nitrobenzene	34.81	409, 452	2.34, 3.27
Methanol	32.58	451, 491	2.96, 3.22
Ethanol	24.36	458, 487	3.03, 3.71
Acetic acid	6.19	412(sd)400-460	4.22
Solid diffuse reflectance	—	397, 401, 462	—

TABLE 2—INFRA-RED DATA FOR FLUORESCHEIN AND ASSIGNMENTS

ν̄, cm ⁻¹	Assignment
705 B.M	
755 B.W	
846 Sd S	
862 B.M	
920 B.M	OH out of plane bending of acid dimer
1110 S	Symmetric stretching C—O—C
1204 S	(i) Antisymmetric C—O—C stretching, (ii) C—O stretching in phenolic OH
1235 S	C—O stretching
1255 S	(i) O—H in plane bending, (ii) C—O stretching
1300 S	(i) Coupling between OH bending and CO stretching in acid dimer, (ii) aromatic ether
1375 S	(i) OH deformation, (ii) aromatic ring
1400 Sd M	(i) Symmetric COO stretching, (ii) Coupling between OH bending and CO stretching of acid dimer
1452 S	Aromatic ring
1472 S	
1588 V.S	(i) Antisymmetric COO stretching, (ii) Aromatic ring
1625 Sd M	Quinoid carbonyl or aromatic ring
1675 B.W	(i) A-associated carbonyl group, (ii) Quinoid carbonyl
3000-300B	OH stretching

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The spectral data of fluorescein is extensive but the recorded results show wide variations¹⁰⁻¹². But in all these investigations, the solutions of fluorescein were made in alkaline media of different strengths. Long time back, Meyer and Fischer¹³ have shown that even a violet coloured solution of fluorescein in boiling alkali gave a spectrum similar to that of normal alkali solutions. Visible and ultraviolet region of the spectrum of alkaline and neutral solutions of fluorescein were studied by Medhi and Watson¹⁴ and Howe¹⁵. Among other workers who studied the spectra, mention may be made of the work of Formanek and Knop¹⁶ and Holmes¹⁷. Moir¹⁸ studied the visible spectrum of the dye in concentrated sulphuric acid. From the scrutiny of spectral data, it is evident that the results are not concordant. The reason may be that either the dye that was used was too much of a commercial type or the method of instrumentation had not reached that perfection to give accurate results.

It is known that fluorescein exists in two physical modifications—red and yellow. It is usual to ascribe the quinoid form to red variety and lactoid structure to the yellow one. According to Orndroff¹⁹, both give identical absorption spectra in a number of solvents and hence both exist in solution in the quinoid state. These very workers took reflectance spectra of another form of fluorescein—bright yellow—crystallised from pyridine solution and found no distinct characteristics of this form. They recorded the absorption spectra of the dye in concentrated sulphuric acid, 75% formic acid and alcoholic solution of HCl and came to the conclusion that in each case fluorescein exists as a salt of the respective acid.

Baeyer²⁰ studied a solution of fluorescein in strong boiling alkali spectrophotometrically and predicted a possible rupture of pyrone ring with the formation of tetrabasic salts. Meyer and Fischer²¹ detected a reasonable resemblance between the absorption of phenolphthalein in weak alkaline solution and that of fluorescein in hot strong alkali. Lewis and Kasha²² have estimated the energy of the phosphorescent state of fluorescein to be 51 K cal higher than the normal singlet state. They have also demonstrated that the phosphorescent triplet state is paramagnetic²³.

The spectral data recorded by the present workers in Table 1 shows the characteristic spectral maxima of the dye in various solvents such as formic acid, methanol, etc. and $\log \epsilon_m$ values. It is clear that the state of fluorescein molecule is apparently different in different solvents and there is a marked "blue shift" as the dielectric constant (ϵ) of the solvent increases.

The infrared lines have to be inspected in the light of three alternative structures as suggested by

Davies *et al*²⁴ in their infra-red studies of the molecule (I, II and III).

The present authors eliminate structure(II) temporarily on the ground that the solid did not show characteristic intense associated carboxyl group absorption extending from 3500-2500 cm^{-1} (Table 2). Besides, they did not observe expected strong absorption near 1630 cm^{-1} due to associated carboxylic and quinoid carbonyl groups in structure(II). However, the expected absorption for the lactoid structure for fluorescein molecule is clearly obtained near 1730 cm^{-1} . Structure(III) is easily eliminated because the strong characteristic frequencies for carboxylate ion (COO^-) namely 1560 and 1430 cm^{-1} are completely absent. Yet another reason, why the present authors do not choose structure (III), is that it hints at paramagnetic susceptibility of the fluorescein, whereas actually on a Gouy magnetic balance, the authors measured the susceptibility of both red and yellow variety to be -0.48 c.g.s.u., a distinctly diamagnetic moiety. Again, the separation of charges between two oxygen centres, in structure (III), also would appreciably reduce the contribution of the structure to the actual state of molecule.

Davies *et al*²⁴, on the basis of their infra-red absorption studies of phenol, phenolphthalein, fluorescein and some alkali derivatives of it, have assigned the lactoid structure (I) to fluorescein.

If now one examines the I.R. data (Table 2) critically, the absorption observed at 1675 cm^{-1} , which may be assigned to associated carboxyl group or/and the quinoid carbonyl group, lends partial support to the quinoid structure²⁵. The broad absorption bands near 920 cm^{-1} and 2500-3500 cm^{-1} also indicate the probable presence of an associated carboxyl group. One of the authors (R.A.B.) used deep red coloured fluorescein for complex studies¹⁻⁵ and this colour suggests a quinoid rather than a lactoid structure.

When one examines the fluorescein molecules, it is found that it possesses coordinating oxygen atom at three positions namely, in the carbonyl group, the hydroxyl group and the carboxyl acid group. Because of the presence of $\text{C}=\text{O}$, $\text{C}-\text{O}$ and OH group in more than one environment in the fluorescein molecule, the task of assigning a particular frequency to a particular group in the metal complexes of fluorescein¹⁻⁵ is difficult. The infra-red spectra of the metal complexes of fluorescein¹⁻⁵, in general, show a definite displacement of OH and

C—O frequencies indicating a specific co-ordination through the OH and C—O linkage in the fluorescein molecule. It is well known that fluorescein forms a disodium salt with replacement of hydrogen atoms in the hydroxyl and the carboxyl groups by sodium atoms. It is, therefore expected that in the case of metal complexes which have been formed under alkaline pH conditions 1-5, there is a distinct possibility of the carboxyl group taking part in the complex formation with metal ions.

Oscillator strengths of fluorescein :

Oscillator strengths of fluorescein have been previously investigated²⁶⁻²⁸ but the solvents employed were not of wide range. The present authors have used same seventeen media to come to a final conclusion regarding oscillator strengths and the method of measurement adopted was the same as mentioned by Jorgensen²⁹ as well as his method of calculations. The spectra of fluorescein in various media have not been presented here but the essential details have been set out in Table 3. The

present work, in the buffer region shows this to be a slightly erroneous conclusion, however the f_{ed} values seem to generally agree. The conclusions are inevitable, in the light of work by Gilman *et al*³¹ and Orndorff *et al*³², that is, in the acidic range of 1M H₂SO₄, a neutral molecule of fluorescein exists and changes to triplet state monocation in subsequent dilutions of sulphuric acid. In the pH range of 5.4 to 10.0 the state of fluorescein is divalent anion. This agrees, to some extent, with the work reported by Lindquist³³ and Cordier and Grossweiner³⁴. They have come to the conclusion, by flash photolysis and pulse radiolysis methods, that at 355 nm, semireduced monoanion, at 394 nm, semireduced dianion, and at 428 nm semioxidised monoanion are formed from fluorescein molecule.

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TABLE 3—RELEVANT DATA FOR THE OSCILLATOR STRENGTHS OF FLUORESC EIN MOLECULE

Solvent or Medium	$\lambda_m(\text{nm})$	$\epsilon_{\text{max}} \times 10^4$	$h(\text{cm}^{-1})$	f
1M H ₂ SO ₄	440	2.96	26580	3.518
2.06M H ₂ SO ₄	438	3.10	14620	2.027
3.2M H ₂ SO ₄	436	3.10	7790	1.095
6.1M H ₂ SO ₄	434	4.80	4800	1.040
7.2M H ₂ SO ₄	433	5.80	5580	1.452
9.02M H ₂ SO ₄	431	6.60	5410	1.580
0.2M HClO ₄	460	1.20	6540	0.3570
0.021M HClO ₄	461	0.98	6790	0.3060
0.126M H ₂ SO ₄	461	1.10	6600	0.3246
KH ₂ (C ₂ O ₄) ₂ H ₂ O (Buffer pH 12.15)	438	0.80	10930	0.3910
Succinate of Sodium Buffer pH=5.4	484	0.73	4110	0.1342
Phosphate of K & Na Buffer pH=8.9	486	0.69	6160	0.1901
Borax Buffer pH=9.18	489	0.66	4640	0.1370
Na-Carbonate Bicarbonate Buffer pH=10.0	494	0.58	29040	0.7532
Acidphthalate Buffer pH=2.09	480	0.76	7930	0.2696
Acetic acid Buffer pH=4.638	462	0.77	29860	1.028
HCl-KCl Buffer pH=2.09	439	0.91	4250	0.1730

symbols ϵ_{max} , h , f and λ have the usual meanings. The oscillator strengths of fluorescein anion reported by Rohatgi²⁸ fall in the range ~ 0.60 whereas the reported values of f in the present work, range from 3.5 (1 M H₂SO₄) to 0.13 (for pH 5.4). Oster and Adelman³⁰ report that the ϵ_{max} of sodium salt of fluorescein, eosin, is 7.25×10^4 1/mole whereas the f_{ed} is of the order of 7.84×10^8 1/mole sec. The

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